

Condensation of Benzotrichloride with Phenols.

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Benzoylphenol or oxybenzophenone was previously obtained by Doebner and Stockmann (*Ber.*, 1877, 10, 1969) together with phenylbenzoate and benzyolphenol-benzoate by the action of benzotrichloride on a mixture of phenol and zinc oxide.

Heiber (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 3677) obtained in a very poor yield (about 1 p. c.) *o*-hydroxybenzophenone by heating a mixture of phenol, benzotrichloride and caustic soda. It has now been found that an alcoholic solution of benzotrichloride (3:1) reacts more satisfactorily with an alkaline solution of phenol at the temperature of the boiling water-bath yielding about 5 p. c. *ortho*-hydroxybenzophenone. The nitrophenols appear not to react with benzotrichloride. The naphthols, however, react more readily with benzotrichloride. With α -naphthol two products are obtained, one soluble in alkali (yield 4 p. c.), reacts with phenylhydrazine and semicarbazide, while the other (yield 16 p. c.) is insoluble in alkali and does not react with phenylhydrazine and semicarbazide. The β -naphthol compound (yield 20 p. c.) also is insoluble in alkali and behaves similarly.

It is concluded that the compound soluble in alkali is the *p*-hydroxynaphthylphenylketone, while the alkali insoluble products are the *o*-compounds undergoing tautomerisation in the following manner,

which explains the insolubility of the compounds in alkali, and also their inactivity towards phenylhydrazine and semicarbazide, probably due to the steric hindrance as suggested by Kehrmann (*Ber.*, 1888, 21, 3315 ; 1890, 23, 3557).

It is interesting to note that *o*-coumaric acid reacts readily with benzotrichloride, forming the corresponding ketone, *p*-coumarylphenylketone (yield 30 p. c.). The compound is presumably the *p*-derivative, as the *o*-substitution product is not ordinarily formed in the case of *o*-coumaric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

o-Hydroxybenzophenone.—A mixture of phenol (30 g.) and benzotrichloride (4 g.) dissolved in alcohol (140 c. c.) was added drop by drop to a solution of caustic soda (55 g. in 90 c. c. water) with constant stirring. The mixture was heated on the boiling water-bath for 8 hours. On acidification a reddish-brown semi-solid mass separated out, which was washed several times with hot water. The dried mass was next washed with petroleum ether to remove the excess of benzotrichloride. It was then dissolved in caustic soda. The alkaline solution cooled to 0° and was then neutralised with acetic acid. The yellowish mass was filtered and the process repeated several times, until a pale yellow solid was obtained. It was finally crystallised from dilute alcohol as pale yellow needles, m. p. 41°, yield 3 g. It was found identical with the compound prepared by Heiber (*loc. cit.*) in an yield of 3.5 g. from 144 g. of phenol.

The *oxime*, obtained by the usual method, crystallised in needles, m. p. 132-33°. It was found identical with the *oxime* (m. p. 133°) prepared by Heiber (*loc. cit.*).

o- & *p*-Hydroxynaphthylphenylketones.—A solution of α -naphthol (10 g.), benzotrichloride (17 g.) and alcohol (40 c. c.) was added to a solution of caustic soda (15 g. in 30 c. c. water) as in the preceding compound. But the temperature was kept between 50-60°. The product, separating on acidification, was washed with water and then with petroleum ether. It was then treated with ammonia to remove the *p*-compound. The *o*-compound was crystallised from boiling chloroform in brownish microcrystalline powder, m. p. 114°, yield 3 g. It is insoluble in water, ether, petroleum ether and ammonia ; sparingly soluble in alcohol, chloroform, benzene and boiling caustic soda ; easily soluble in acetone. It gives no

coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 82.40; H, 5.21. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 82.25; H, 4.83 per cent.).

The ammoniacal solution containing the *p*-compound when acidified with acetic acid, yielded a brick-red powder which was crystallised from very dilute alcohol, m. p. 162-64°, yield 1 g. It is easily soluble in alcohol, ether, chloroform and acetone; insoluble in water, benzene and petroleum ether. It gives a greenish orange coloration with ferric chloride. It was found identical with the compound (m. p. 164-65°) prepared from 1-hydroxy-naphthyl 2-carboxylic acid and benzotrichloride without any alkali (D. R. P., 378908, 378909; Swiss Pat., 98559). (Found: C, 82.1; H, 4.64. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 82.25; H, 4.83 per cent.)

2-Hydroxy- α -naphthylphenylketone.—The reaction was carried out with β -naphthol, benzotrichloride, alcohol and alkali as in the first compound. The product, separating on acidification was washed with alkali and finally with water. It was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and chloroform as a brick-red microcrystalline powder, m. p. 174°, yield 5 g. It is insoluble in water, cold alkali, alcohol and petroleum ether; soluble with difficulty in ether and boiling caustic soda; easily soluble in chloroform, acetone and benzene; does not give any coloration with ferric chloride. It was found identical with the compound prepared from β -naphthol and benzotrichloride without any alkali (D. R. P., 378908, 378909; Swiss Pat., 98559). (Found: C, 82.51; H, 5.31. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 82.25; H, 4.83 per cent.).

o-Coumarylphenylketone.—A solution of *o*-coumaric acid (15 g.), benzotrichloride (20 g.) and alcohol (100 c. c.) was added to a solution of caustic soda (25 g. in 41 c. c. water) as in the first compound. The heating and stirring were continued for 12 hours. On acidification, a black tarry liquid separated out which was washed with petroleum ether to remove the excess of benzotrichloride. The product was dissolved in alkali and reprecipitated with acetic acid. The process was repeated for several times, until a brownish solid was obtained, which was next boiled with water to remove the unchanged *o*-coumaric acid. The mixture was filtered hot and the residue crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellowish microcrystalline powder, m. p. 188°, yield 7.2 g. It is insoluble in water, chloroform and petroleum ether; moderately soluble in alcohol and easily soluble in ether. (Found: C, 71.78; H, 4.57. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.64; H, 4.47 per cent.).

Silver salt was prepared in the usual way from ammonium salt as yellow powder. (Found: Ag, 28·77. $C_{16}H_{11}O_4$ Ag requires Ag, 28·80 per cent.).

The *phenylhydrazone*, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from alcohol as reddish tiny needles, m. p. 120° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7·7. $C_{22}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires N, 7·8 per cent.).

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